

PHILOLOGICAL SCIENCES

RESEARCH HISTORY AND DEVELOPMENT DYNAMICS OF THE PROCESS OF WORD FORMATION IN LANGUAGES WITH DIFFERENT SYSTEMS

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Abstract

The purpose of the article is to look at the factors that make the word creation process necessary for the creation of new lexical units, to investigate and reveal the similar and different features of the word creation process in English and Azerbaijani languages, which are languages with different systems. Checking the theoretical-methodological part of the research work based on practical knowledge is its main task.

Keywords: word formation, derivational, affixation, productive.

In life, the first acquaintance with the environment, objects and events begins through acquired experiences. As a result of attention, watching and observation, first of all, information about these objects and events is received through sense organs, and then an image of them is formed in the human mind. Receiving information about objects and events with sense organs is a direct process. The human mind naming them in a certain way is the next process and stage. Objects and events newly entered into consciousness are associated with other existing objects and events due to certain common characteristics, and common signs are sought between them. According to these aspects, they are named. The word is known as the main unit of the lower level of the language as an expression of concepts and concepts in thinking. Since word and name are closely related to each other, they cannot be separated from each other. However, we must not forget that the word is a means of communication, and the name is its nominative function. As a result of their use, words have a nominative function and are considered names. Not every word in the language, only words with lexical meaning can be nouns.

Language develops in a fluid process over time, and the vocabulary of the language expands and enriches due to newly created words. Words and expressions that have just entered the language, are newly created within the language or already exist in the language, are used for specific purposes in oral, literary language and among certain groups of people. Not all lexical units in the language exist, but the history of many of them is known and it is possible to determine them. For example, computer, telephone, radio, telegram. The emergence and use of the words we have listed in the language is related to the invention and production of the telegram, telephone and computer, radio.

The creator and bearer of the word is the people. During the formative period, people felt the need to express their feelings and thoughts, needs, danger and something else to each other. As a result of all this, words were created in a natural way, in the process of social labor activity of people and through mutual exchange. First, work, and then the process of speech formed the ape-like human brain and became the

stimulus for its further perfection and transformation into the modern human brain.

The word has been given many definitions. However, its scientific definition has been studied more by linguists. At first glance, the answer to this profound question, which we think is very simple, has not yet been given a complete, scientific answer in the science of linguistics. E.M. Galkina-Fedoruk writes: "A word is a unit that makes up the vocabulary of a language. The position of the word in the general system of the language should be clarified from different perspectives. Because language is related to the economic and political life of the society, scientific, technical, artistic-aesthetic, production-labour activities, social-household issues, etc. it is a means of all and all kinds of relations". In addition, "Word is a linguistic unit used to serve the purposes of communication, expressing any fact of reality, as its natural matter, through phonetic composition. Therefore, the word, as the main unit of the vocabulary, reveals the fullness of its nature and its true meaning within the related speech.

"Language reflects the history of the entire nation, its life, dreams and hopes, pains and sufferings, joys and achievements from the moment of its creation. However, despite the great importance of language in human life, the problem of the word as its main unit has not yet been adequately resolved."

The word and its properties have interested people since ancient times. Even in ancient Rome and Greece, linguists worked to determine the meaning of a word, and they had important debates about its place in a sentence and language.

If we look at the definition of the word from the point of view of modern linguistics, we will see that the word is considered to be the most important, the most basic unit of the language. Among the language levels, word creation has its own place. This is because word formation is considered a basic language level, while other levels of language have their own specific unit. Because it does not have a special unit of its own.

The process of word creation is learning about the structure of words, the rules and methods of their formation. In word creation, the formation of language on the basis of internal development laws is clearly demonstrated. Word creation is taught and taught in

linguistics as a part of lexicon or grammar, but teaching word creation as part of the lexicon is considered more appropriate by many linguists, because it is impossible to imagine the newly created lexical unit outside the vocabulary of the language.

As stated by Hasrat Hasanov, the concept of "speech creation" in language can be used in synchronic and diachronic aspects. Synchronous and diachronic word creation has different content. In diachronic word creation, it is investigated with the help of which means derivative words are formed. In synchronous word creation, we are talking about the means by which the derivational (word creation) meaning of derived words is expressed. Synchronous word formation studies the relation of language units to each other, while diachronous word formation studies the transition of one unit to another unit.

Word formation in English has been studied and researched as a separate important topic of linguistics. In its original meaning, the word creation term is used to express the process of constant creation of new lexical units in the language. This process refers to certain and numerous linguistic processes that occur in the language, including the process of creating new words in the language and enriching the language composition. As a result, this process is expressed in the language in the form of the term "word creation".

However, the term "word creation" in its second meaning bears the name of a branch of linguistics that studies the process of formation of lexical units.

Although word formation is considered an independent field in linguistics, it cannot be considered separately from other aspects of linguistics, namely syntax, morphology, and lexicology. Academician V.V.Vinogradov, E.S.Kubryakova and other linguists in their scientific works and researches have given detailed information about the mutual and strong connection of word creation with the other aspects of the language that we have listed. According to E.S. Kubryakova, "the main essence of the word creation process is the emergence of new names, units, and soon such names turn into words. The term word creation literally means naming the word creation process.

In word creation, the structure and meaning of a creative word is formed based on the basis of word creation tools and word creation sources. The existence of the relationship between the original meaning of the word and the derived meaning of the newly created word makes it possible to explain and explain it, from its initial meaning to the creation of the word, and helps to reveal the true meaning of the word.

Word creation is not only a mechanical process, but also based on certain rules and laws of the language, it is carried out through methods and methods that have already become a system. These methods are studied and researched in different languages and are used as a base in the process of word creation as appropriate. In general linguistics literature, more detailed and extensive information is given about these word-creating methods and tools: word-creating through conversion, word-creating through affixation, substantivization (a type of word-creating that has more than one motivated base), abbreviation (UNICEF,

formed in the form of combining the initials of words, Words like AFFA, FBI, etc. are meant).

There are two main bases for the enrichment of the vocabulary of the language:

1. The language's own base - vocabulary fund.
2. Other languages.

English and Azerbaijani languages, like other languages of the world, are constantly in contact with other languages and, as a result, are developing and updating. If we compare it with the Azerbaijani language, we can say that because English is an international language, it is more influenced than other languages and, in turn, affects other languages more. National words make up 30% of the rich vocabulary of the English language, and borrowed words make up the remaining 70%. Borrowed words make up 15% of the Azerbaijani language. As we mentioned, the reasons for the introduction of borrowed words into the language depend to a great extent on the history of that language, the states it has been in contact with, occupied or warred with throughout history, and socio-political relations. Borrowed words that entered any language, as well as English and Azerbaijani, are selected from national words according to their phonetic, morphological structure and grammatical forms.

Expanding and enriching the vocabulary of the language at the expense of its own national base is considered more progressive. Thus, when new lexical units in the language are formed at the expense of the language's own national base, the new words and the form of their formation will be known to the speaker of the language. Word creation is closely related to the grammar and vocabulary system to which it belongs, because words create a new lexical unit by accepting a word or a suffix according to the requirements of the grammatical rules of the language to which they belong, and in this way, enriches and expands the vocabulary of the language to which it belongs:

-Word formation by adding various suffixes to the word root

- Word correction by adding a word to the word root

Forming a new word by adding various suffixes to the word root is called a morphological method in the linguistics literature.

Word-formation pathways are divided into two types: productive and non-productive: all active word-formation pathways are called productive, and non-productive word-formation pathways that are not used for a long time and intensively.

Productive ways: affixation, conversion, shortening, clipping, compounding or composition.

Unproductive ways: stress interchange, sound interchange, back formation, onomatopoeia or sound imitation, reduplication.

Affixation is considered one of the most used and most productive ways of word creation in the history of language. The essence of this way usually consists in creating a new lexical unit by adding suffixes to the word root in different directions. If we look at Araki's ideas about suffixation in modern English, we will see that the main function of suffixation in modern English

is to create another new part of speech from one part of speech; another function is to change the lexical meaning of a word belonging to the same part of speech. In this regard, two types of imagers are distinguished: word modifiers, i.e. lexical (derivational) and word modifiers, i.e. grammatical (functional). In addition, we can group suffixes as national and derivational according to their origin, and as suffixes, prefixes and infixes according to the place of addition to the word root. Examples of frequently used suffixes in modern English are -ism(realism), -ist(perfectionist), -ery(poetry,peasantry), -able(unbearable), -th (strength), -er (writer), -ic(public),-ive(active),-ship(friendship),-dom(kingdom),-hood(brotherhood), -ful(delightful),-ous(glorious),-

ess(actress),-ate(stimulate) and so on. we can give an example.

References

1. Arnold I.V. "The English Word", Moscow, 1986.
2. Bain A. "A Higher English Grammar", New York, 1904.
3. Bauer L. "English Word Formation", Cambridge; London; New York, 1983.
4. Biese M. "Origin and Development of Conversion in English", Helsinki,1941.
5. Bradley H. "The Making of English", London, 1937.
6. Craig D. "The Essential of English Grammar", New York, 1871.